

BLOOD ROTATION OF THE SYSTEM PHYSICIST BASICS

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ANNOTATION.

Blood rotation of the system physicist basics , physiological and biomechanics structure learner to the field related , of blood movement and in it oxygen , gases , salts and another substances to come learned one how many physicist from concepts consists of This is common blood directly (blood rotation) and blood veins between has been rotation , rotation speed and of blood viscosity with depends . Blood circulation , transportation of substances and oxygen , carbon dioxide , and another many substances to arrive process own into takes _ This is the process another organs , muscles and organs own into takes _

Key words: oxygen, carbon dioxide , erythrocyte , leukocyte, plasma, platelet .

INTRODUCTION

Blood rotation speed , one per minute blood size reflection to continue represents _ This is speed average management because of the condition different organs and vital conditions in it of blood necessary has been size change can _ Blood viscosity , blood rotation and veins between substances from each other separate throwing to the list received complexity explains . Blood viscosity , erythrocytes , leukocytes (arrow cells), platelets and plasma such as of components consists of Blood from the collection organs , muscles and of blood another transport to the part for installed blood veins system blood rotation system another parts with depends . Blood in the collection bloods oxygen , glucose , and another substances to organs delivered to give for service does _ Blood rotation organs , blood rotation for important important have has been are organs . Blood distribution , their activities provide and of blood rotation for strong to be road Created . Walking processes of blood viscosity and rotation speed manages. This main physicist bases , blood rotation normal and _ efficient work provides . Blood straight away circulation of blood vital substances with to be filled and different organs between certain in part stealing arrival , component structure and transport functions through vital external and internal conditions in storage big important have _

blood rotation of the system the work activity disorder. Blood rotation of the system the work activity violation , any reasons , that's it including physical activity , hormones , genetics factors or external factors because of to be can _ Such circumstances exactly diseases , systemic vital of manuals intermediate the pressure change , oxygen deficiency , infections , rest of processes violation and another reasons with depends to be can _ Anemia , blood hemoglobin of the amount decrease , hematocrit (erythrocytes amount) and erythrocytes the number from the norm lower to be because of surface will come . Anemia reason has been of reasons one , top in quantity blood the way to create possibility providing vitamins and minerals _ that it is not to be can _ Blood the way in creating important role who plays hematocrit quantity and hemoglobin contained decrease , blood rotation efficient process in providing important _ Any _ reasons with this amounts decreased when it 's gone blood rotation of the system efficient performance and important substances delivered not to give take coming can _

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Blood rotation of the system viscosity of processes violation blood rotation efficient to provide effect do it take can _ This circumstances blood rotation the way situations take coming and vital to organs delivered not to give take coming can _ Blood in the collection veins , blood to organs and to structures in delivery big role they play They are blood rotation in management important .. Blood efficient rotation and vital to organs delivered to be given is broken . This is your blood straight away rotation in providing main is the environment. Blood rotation of the system the work activity disorder , illness , vital conditions and genetic of properties one series reasons take coming can _ That's why for , any in indications , diseases about doctor or expert with communication to do need. Blood rotation of the system physicist the basics determination There are various laboratory and clinical instruments for These tools are blood composition of blood chemical and physiological properties of blood device and flow cells , blood indicators , hematocrit and another indicators study , management and is used to provide an audit trail. The following tools learning and valuation for wide comprehensive data will give . These tools are automated blood used to perform the analysis . Blood blood analyzers _ reading , device and flow cells , indicators , hematocrit the amount and another indicators read , identify and to count help gives. Blood indicators of blood chemical structure and changes check used for These are tools between blood in the system

substances , waters and another indicators study to learn which provides devices included .

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Hematocrit , blood sticky and plasma of division the amount represents _ Hematocrit devices , blood straight away rotation and of blood of the mucous membrane efficient work to check help Hemoglobinometers are used to read and determine the amount of hemoglobin in the blood . They are blood oxygen transport _ and deliver ability to see possibility gives. Blood device and flow cells in the microscope will be checked . These are microscopes of blood of cells number , shape and device of cells chemical structure learning for used. Blood indicators and blood composition and his chemical structure to check help will give . These tools are blood of the composition amount of , its glucose , lipids and another of substances quantity about information gives. This tools , blood rotation used to obtain information about various features of the system and its operation. It provides comprehensive information to explain the process of managing examinations, diseases, changes and treatment.

Summary

Blood rotation , above given processes organize is enough and blood rotation system (blood vein , veins , arteries) . own movement does. This sentence under , " blood rotation of the system physicist essence " _ to understand for many physiological , biochemical and physical to concepts have to be necessary _ These are concepts medicine in the sciences is studied and in treatment of blood structure and rotation with depends issues analysis in doing is used. Blood rotation of the system physicist the basics of blood rotation and structure with depends . This is the structure and rotation processes , oxygen and carbon in dioxide exchange , immune system , and of blood cleaning such as processes own into takes _ The following main physicist to the basics has: b u red blood veins , oxygen to themselves to orgons _ delivers _ That's all vital in the direction of blood immune system which provides part organize is enough They are to infections against to fight , to damage against alternative to be and of blood cleaning participation is enough A lot openable this particles , injured places corrects and of blood to the movement help is giving This is your blood himself organize which structural of elements common size expressive amount _ Blood from water organize found structure change and his to changes against viscosity characteristic of blood in circulation own importance performs _ Blood erythrocytes through oxygen and carbon of dioxide cleansing for the body

important has been physical from processes is one. This features of blood burning and rotation for important has been blood correction system represents. This main concepts , blood rotation of the system physicist the basics in understanding help will give .

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